

LINGUOPOETICS OR THE RELATIONSHIP OF LINGUISTICS AND ARTISTIC LITERATURE

Kuchkorov KHoshimjon KHasanzoda

Lecturer of the Department of Uzbek Literature
of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Abstract. Linguistics is closely related to literature. Because language as a means of communication is not only a simple system of symbols containing certain information, but also a powerful tool for influencing the listener. The first task of language is the object of study of traditional and systemic-structural linguistics, and the second task is the object of study of linguopoetics.

Key words: linguistics, art, linguopoetics, word, means of artistic image, parts of linguopoetics, philological analysis.

In world linguistics today, the study of the language of a literary text from a structural-semantic point of view and the use in this process of methods of statistical, component, comparative historical and cognitive analysis are of current importance. Among other things, understanding the intertextual purpose in the language of classical poetry, determining the essence of philosophical and historical terms in the text of poetry, determining the logical function of mystical terms remains one of the basic principles of modern linguistics. In this sense, the discovery of a number of multi-layered symbolic and metaphorical meanings characteristic of classical poetry, clarification of the level of lexical, mystical and mystical units in a literary text is considered one of the important factors determining the development of poetry from linguistics.

As a result of the integration of linguistics and literary studies in world science, new types of linguapoetic and linguistic trends in philological research have emerged. This direction has made it possible to simultaneously study the linguistic and poetic

features of a work of art, and in recent years has created the basis for the emergence of many new scientific studies. Therefore, such questions as the definition of literary and social trends and the reality of life in classical poetic language, the etymology of words and symbols, their theoretical and linguistic foundations, the position of the system of mystical terms in poetry, etc. arise. .have knowledge. determining the creative abilities and creative power of the poet is one of the main tasks facing us.

Since independence, new trends have emerged in the field of linguistics and the study of the language of classical poetry, among other fields. In particular, the linguistic and mystical interpretation of words and symbols in the language of classical poetry, which is the lexical embodiment of artistic language, as well as compositional, cognitive, comparative and historical features of lexical-semantic units in the lyrical language. works are being discussed. as an urgent matter.

The tradition of linguistic and poetic analysis of individual texts originates from the works of Academician V. V. Vinogradov. However, despite the fundamental nature of the scientist's works, they do not provide a final answer to the questions of what determines the uniqueness of classical works of art and what methods are necessary to determine the elements of language that have aesthetic significance. In connection with the linguapoetic study of literary text, one can also mention B.V. Mashevsky, L.V. Shcherba, L. Spitzer and others.

Based on all of the above, the linguistic and poetic analysis of a work of art appears through the analysis and systematization of the elements of the linguistic organization of the text, including the "image of the world" and "image of the world." author" from the point of view of a certain aesthetic ideal. This type of linguistic text analysis is characterized by partial entry into the field of literary analysis. Linguistic and poetic analysis of the text is very close to philological analysis and allows us to fully elucidate the cultural and historical content of the work and its literary features.

Linguistic and poetic analysis of the text includes the following information: determination of genre and thematic features of the text; description of artistic styles and their role; review of linguistic means in relation to the figurative system.

Linguistic poetics is the placement of words and images in a text, leading to an understanding of the author's meaning (building a chain of words and images associated with a name).

The method of linguapoetic analysis of the text includes the following: Identifying the most important words in meaning, clarifying the connection between these words, determining by what means the writer was able to express his inner impression. Interpretation of literary text.

In linguistics, the concept of "functional expressive language" is sometimes used as a synonym for "functional poetic language", "functional artistic language" and "functional aesthetic language". However, it should be said that the "aesthetic" function of language is more active and important than other functions. Special linguist D. Shimelevba said: "The only function of aesthetic language is the creation of a work of art, but the modern process is a lie, and the form of expression is a straw man with the influence of time and the function of language." It happens that the speaker does not care about the content of the speech, but sometimes it is a lie, and the form and style of speech is very important. One way of communication is conversation, the other is funny. , the more interesting the speech, the more it imitates and the smaller the volume of the tongue, the better it affects speech. 10 It must be emphasized that the task of aesthetic language is deep study in the field of linguapoetics. Also, the task of aesthetic language is to consider the text. In fact, the task of aesthetics is different from that of a linguist or literary critic. After all, this is the task of simultaneously studying the theory of literature, the history of literature and poetics, as well as the history of language, lexicology, semasiology, etymology and grammar. The problem of functional aesthetic language is at the same time in the sphere of science. The main goal of this science is to understand the meaning and content of the text. Text analysis

is based on artistic principles, especially linguapoetic ones. The role of a specific model is played by the image, that is, poetic, phonographic, lexical, morphological and syntactic means in the text. Scientific text analysis is associated with art and science, linguistics, literary criticism, textual criticism, speech culture, stylistics, philosophy, ethics, aesthetics and logic.

The goal is to study the basic language of the language in the direction of linguapoetics. The problem is that languages have different functions. This is the fourth or fifth task of the modern linguist of modern literature. 1. Functional communication consists of basic language communication skills. 2. The purpose of expression is to express thoughts and feelings. 3. Constructive tasks - the task is to create an idea, create order and express a certain style of the map. 4. Objectives - objectives and experience and wisdom of society. The application is called the "functional expression" language, and the business research language is called the "task language", "task language" and "aesthetic task language". However, he noted that the concept of "functional-aesthetic language" is more familiar than the philology of literature. Naturally, the function of the concept is an aesthetic metaphor; a number of concepts are also born, including expression, art and poetry. The phrase "To whom" is different; the function of the concept of a circle is an aesthetic attitude. Of course, every work is art and other tasks are practical language, but the task of aesthetics is first and foremost a teacher and guide. As the literary critic said: "The text is artistic, but each text is unusual, it has a special task. But when the partner is complex, the task is communicative and a special text appears." "The goal is an aesthetic presentation that evokes envy." It should be noted that the aesthetics of language is manifested in the sphere of work, the work of the text is only artistically based, and the form of language cannot fulfill the tasks of everyday speech. In this regard, the words of the linguist D.N. Shmelev are interesting: "There is more than one work on the task of language (the task of aesthetics). Each time he pays attention to the form of the sentence, the style of expression and the scope of the task. The scientist emphasizes that when speaking, the form of external speech

is the same, the expression of value capabilities is linguistic attention, and the function of aesthetic language is manifested in its original form, i.e. The purpose of language is to be active in the moment, and in this case it is not only who is speaking that is important, but also the style of expression. Mavridi Sukhani Zinda, Bisiyar Latifahoy Dar Varandi Musirati Harruza, Latifanamo Laughter, Suhanoni Amik, Taqlid ba Garan Gaira have attractive linguistic signs, artistic and expressive talent, the function of aesthetic language is clearly visible in the language. The goal is to study the language of linguapoetics and understanding of art, but the function of language is aesthetic. It should be said that the main function of the emergence of language is artistic work on an aesthetic text, and the nature of its study is theological or literary. For this there must be literary disciplines, literary theory, literary history, poetics and linguistics, linguistic stylistics, history of language, lexicology, semantics, etymology, grammar. The purpose of the problem is the aesthetics of language, the complexity of the problem and science. The goal of the program is to have a certain level of ability to use text in writing, linguistic units of text, features of text and features of language and background, the student's ability to develop linguistic and poetic features of the text. sample, and this is the first step.

This is the basis of the science of linguapoetics and has many followers. Near the shower door. Because in the analysis method, the value of each text is an individual requirement. The selection method is necessary and useful for a narrowly selected text poem, but not very useful for a narrowly selected text poem. It is rarely known that the text of linguapoetics analyzed by the method has more content than poetry. This is an analysis of the form of the linguapoetic method of analyzing the behavior of the text of a poem. In the usual analysis of the linguistic text of a poem, a gift is a word instrument based on a spontaneous verse, for example, a verse, a rubab, a tawaqf, a song, a tawaqf picture. However, according to the method of analysis, it is impossible to apply a methodological template and correlation of persons to all texts of the poem, that is, according to the method of analysis, certain, individual requirements are imposed on

each text. poems. The main task is to first determine the unity of the leading word of the text of the poem and determine the line (dominant). If in Alomata the dominant is correct and clear, then the analysis of linguapoetics is clear and at least scientifically substantiated.

The meaning and content of the scientist's poems are determined by the lyrics: a) semantic meaning, b) meaningful poetry. It has different characteristics in terms of attitude and content. The meaning of the poem is that the text of the poem is more pronounced when the poem is recited, and the conceptual meaning of the poem is less. In most cases, the analysis of literature and the text of a poem is the result of the poem, it is difficult to understand the complete point of view of the poem, the linguapoetic meaning of the poet.

So, it is clear that analysis of each text is necessary to evaluate the merits of the poet or friend. It is impossible to choose any method that suits the text of the poem. The text of the analysis conceptually corresponds to the content of the poem. The analysis of the text by the author of the poem is purely lyrical, the content of the poem is not high, but he is considered a scientist in the field of education.

Linguistic poetics is a shortened form of linguistic poetics and studies the artistic and aesthetic functions of linguistic units (phonetic, morphemic, lexical, etc.) used in works of art, the connotative function of language. In other words, linguopoetics is a branch of linguistics that studies artistic speech.

The subject of linguapoetics is a set of linguistic units used in a work of art that provide the necessary aesthetic effect for the writer to realize his artistic intent; The purpose of linguistic analysis is to determine how this or that linguistic unit (word, phrase, syntactic structure) was included by the author in the process of creating a literary word, how this or that combination of linguistic means leads to the creation of a linguistic unit. this aesthetic effect. it must be purposeful" (Zadornova V.Ya. Oral artistic production in different languages as a subject of linguistic research: Diss. ... Doctor of Philology. - M.: 1992.-P.59).). The main object of study of linguopoetics is

a literary text; through its analysis, the artist's artistic skill, characteristic style, use of linguistic resources and the writer's attitude to the national language are studied.

In recent years, the linguapoetic study of the language of a work of art has been the focus of many scientific studies. Because language and literature have always complemented each other and developed harmoniously. Therefore, our linguists, based on such research, develop methods that are used in the study of literary texts from the point of view of language and literature. In particular, when conducting a linguistic study of a literary text, it is necessary to pay special attention to such issues as the aesthetic impact of the word, the compatibility of meaning and content, the individual style of the author in linguapoetic analysis, and its essence. and the aesthetic function of a literary text, analysis of artistically updated vocabulary that increases the aesthetic effect of a literary text. For this reason, an independent field of text linguistics, called "linguopoetics," is attracting increasing attention from researchers. According to the Russian linguist V.V. Vinogradov, the task of linguopoetics is to study the aesthetic function of linguistic units in a work of art. Thus, at the intersection of linguistics and literary criticism, a new direction of philology arises - linguopathy, i.e. a corresponding direction of linguistics and literary criticism, revealing the possibilities of expressing the aesthetic effect of the artistic works of a writer or poet. . the scientist believes, with the help of linguistic means.

German philologist Karl Voeckler says that "All elements of language form the basis of stylistic means of expression."

In the field of linguistics, much work has been done to study the language of literary works. These studies are based on the unique style of each writer in creating a work of art, the ability to use words, the ability to use the tools of artistic image, and in this context the richness and beauty of the creativity of any language is revealed. .

Artistic speech is considered a means of expressing artistic creativity. In the history of philology, the terms language of a work of art and poetic language are often encountered. Although the concepts expressed by these terms are very close to each

other, they differ from each other in some aspects. Concepts such as “image”, “style”, “artistic language”, “stylistics”, “poetics” are concepts related to the language of works of art and linguapoetics.

According to V.P. Grigoriev, artistic language as an integral subject tends to break down into functionally different parts and fragments.

In practice, only individual parts of the whole object are analyzed. This main work is considered the language of the work of art. It seems that artistic speech is a broader concept than the language of a work of art. Enables the expressive function of language. The language of a work of art is a form, a piece of artistic speech.

Linguistic poetics, which studies artistic speech, covers the artistic and aesthetic function of units at all levels of the language system. At the phonetic-phonological level, phonetic units can also perform an artistic and aesthetic function. In particular, the repetition of one voice and one syllable is a means of beauty and expression of poetry. In a poetic text, the aesthetic possibilities of speech sounds are quickly and easily realized. Because the poem has a wonderful tone. This tone is achieved through the methodical use of sounds. The poem uses phonetic techniques such as alliteration (repetition of consonants), assonance (repetition of vowels), gemination (layering of consonants). In prose, expressiveness is ensured by such phonetic techniques as lengthening vowels, consonants, repetition of sounds, incorrect pronunciation of words, raising or lowering the voice. The ability to “accurately” express the laws associated with the methodical use of voices on the line is limited. However, the pronunciation and pronunciation are the same. phonographic instruments with its help you can achieve. Even in the times of Plato and Aristotle, the problem of pronouncing a word and translating it into writing attracted the attention of thinkers. Although it has nothing to do with speech, the harmony of tones associated with the pronunciation of a word, the letters in a word, has been a source of inspiration for great philosophers. They tried to attach special significance to the sounds that made up the word that had not yet acquired their meaning and tone.

At the lexical level, the use of lexemes in a metaphorical sense (metaphor, metonymy, etc.), exaggeration, and exaggeration increase efficiency and effectiveness. linguopoetics is the subject of investigation. In addition, during the lexical analysis of a literary text in the language of a literary work, synonyms, synonyms, antonyms, ambiguous, historical and archaic words, new works, dialect words, foreign words and colloquial expressions are determined. the essence of the work is explained.

When analyzing the linguistic features of a literary text, it is necessary to take into account the phenomena associated with the use of morphological units. The aesthetic function of morphological units means “the expression of expressiveness - feelings through special word forms, as well as through the special use of word forms with a certain grammatical meaning and function.” Expressiveness is clearly observed in words that have positive and negative meanings. In the linguistic study of a literary text, it is necessary to identify units that have such semantic aspects and pay attention to what category they belong to, in whose speech, for what purpose, in relation to whom and in what situation they were used. . As a rule, words expressing meanings such as affection, respect, honor, pleasure, greatness, solemnity are words that have a positive boundary of meaning. For example: little girl, orgilai, girigittonbe like my son, my white, my water, my lion, my fighter, my sugar, my sweet. Words with negative connotations include words that express subjective attitudes such as hatred, arrogance, contempt, arrogance, contempt, hate, anger, sarcasm, and rudeness. Identifying and assessing the factors that create such meanings is the basis of linguistic analysis. In the Uzbek language there is a diminutive form with the suffixes -cha, -chak, -chak; The form of the game is created using the affixes -chan, -han, -oi, -(a)lok. Meanings such as respect, insult, sarcasm, generalization and classification are created using the suffix -lar. The suffix -gina means boundary, love, intimacy. During the analysis, not all morphological units used in the text are taken into account, but those morphological features whose aesthetic purpose is clearly visible and the writer’s artistic intent is expressed. For example, one of the most commonly used artistic tools is repetition.

From a linguistic point of view, the purpose of using morphological parallelism is studied - a methodological tool that arises when repeating morphological units. Notes can also be made regarding the use of anthroponyms belonging to a family of names for a specific purpose. Indeed, among the nouns used in a work of art, there are names that have a special stylistic purpose and help determine the writer's artistic intent.

To ensure the effectiveness of artistic speech, the syntactic method is widely used. Syntactic gradation, syntactic synonymy, special use of conjunctions, antithesis, monologue, silence, inversion, repetition, rhetorical question, anaphora, epiphora, ellipsis, alliteration, rhetorical address, syntactic parallelism, emotional sentences, etc. is considered the object of study of syntactic poetics. The formation of artistic speech is served by such phenomena as the placement of sentence fragments, repetition of the same fragments as part of a sentence.

The basis of the artistically updated lexical apparatus is the logical concepts of comparison, comparison, revival, which are of great importance in the analysis of artistic text. It is known that conveying meaning based on comparison is called metaphor. Metaphor is one of the most common ways of creating figurative meaning. Since linguistic metaphors mainly perform the function of naming, they do not reflect stylistic coloring, expressiveness, and, consequently, a subjective attitude towards the subject of speech that they represent. Only the scope of the meaning of a certain word expands and serves to define new concepts.

It is known that coloristics is the science of color and is based on color culture and language, color harmony. Each color in the culture of every nation, in the work of every artist, has its own linguistic and cultural content and meaning. A person also imagines his life using the example of different colors. The color lexeme is reflected in a person's imagination in different colors depending on his mood and mental state. In particular, white is a symbol of purity, goodness and honesty, and black is a symbol of sadness and evil. Bright pink, red, airy colors personify a person's joyful mood, black, gray, brown, on the contrary, personify a depressed mood.

In linguistics, in addition to common metaphors, there are animation and synaesthetic metaphors. Animation is one of the important tools that complement artistic speech with clarity. Animation is a form of metaphor. Animation is a visual technique that is created by transferring the characteristics of people to inanimate objects, natural phenomena, animals, birds, and birds.

Among the lexical means of artistic realization, metonymy plays an important role in increasing the aesthetic effect of a work of art. It is known that metonymy refers to the transfer of meaning based on the proximity and connection of events and objects. Metonymy is also based on comparison. In metonymy, characteristics of objects that are generally different from each other are compared and renamed, even if they are related to each other by external or internal characteristics.

SoLinguistic poetics is divided into phonetic poetics, lexical poetics and syntactic poetics, depending on the level of the language being studied, artistic and aesthetic functions. The study of each type of linguopoetics and determination of their relationship is one of the important tasks of modern linguistics. Linguistic analysis of a literary text serves to determine the poetic capabilities of this language and assess the author's ability to use the linguistic resources available in the language fund.

In the initial research works created in the field of linguopoetics, the main attention was paid to the functional and stylistic features of lexical units, and later on the linguopoetic features of grammatical units, the peculiarities of the use of each linguistic unit in a literary text. a separate object of study.

Each linguistic unit, each linguistic event performs its function in the formation of artistic speech, which has emotional expressiveness and high aesthetic forms. The phenomenon of stupidity and excess of speech cannot be excluded from this task. The meeting of the phenomenon of economy and excess in a literary text, of course, depends on a specific linguistic goal, and a full analysis of this issue requires many studies.

REFERENCES:

1. Kuchkorov KH.KH. Some Features Of The Theory Of Translation Of Tajik Literature Of The Twentieth Century. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. Vol. 12, Issue 05, May 2022. 521-526 p.
2. Kuchkorov KH.KH. The Role of Literary Translation in the Formation of Literary Communication and Literary Influence (Based on Paulo Coelho's Work "The Alchemist"). *Miasto Przyszłości Kielce*. Vol. 31 (2023), p 32-35
3. Kuchkorov KH.KH. The Position of Literary Translation in the Formation of Cultural Relations. *Research journal of trauma and disability studies*. Volume: 02, Issue: 01, Jan – 2023. p 24-26
4. Kuchkorov KH.KH. Morphological and Syntactic Changes in Literary Translation. *Nexus: Journal of Innovative Studies of Engineering Science (JISES)*, Volume: 02, Issue: 01, 2023, p 1-3
5. Kuchkorov KH.KH. Artistic representation of the realities of life in "The Alchemist" by Paulo Coelho. *ARES*. Volume 4, Issue 6, 2023. p 331-338.
6. Kuchkorov KH.KH. Problems Of Artistic Recreation In Translated Works (As An Example Of Translations Of The Work Of "The Alchemist"). *International Journal of Language Learning and Applied Linguistics*. ISSN: 2835-1924. Volume 2, No 10, Oct-2023, p 14-23
7. Kuchkorov KH.KH. Analysis Of The Main Characters Of The Novel "The Alchemist" By Paulo Coelho. *"Экономика и социум" №6(109) -2 2023*. p 244-247
8. Йўлдошев М. Бадиий матн лингвопоэтикаси. – Тошкент: Фан, 2008. – 160 б.
9. Йўлдошев М. Бадиий матн ва унинг лингвопоэтик таҳлили асослари. – Тошкент, 2007.
10. Quchqorov H.H. Tarjimon, tarjima va matn. "Тил ва адабиёт таълими" журнали. Махсус сон, 2022. 44-46 б.